

COMPOSITION AND STRUCTURE OF THE OWNERS' CLASS

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In the process of transition to a market economy in Uzbekistan, the formation and development of the owner class is one of the important aspects of the socio-economic life of the country. In this thesis, we analyze the composition and structure of the ownership class, its formation factors and its role in society.

The main part

The class of owners is an important layer of the society of Uzbekistan, and its formation and development are closely related to economic changes during the years of independence of the country. The emergence and evolution of this class is directly related to the privatization process, which is one of the main directions of the socio-economic development strategy of Uzbekistan.

The composition and structure of the property class is complex and multifaceted, and it is constantly changing and developing. Professor A. As Olmasov noted, "The class of owners in Uzbekistan is not homogeneous, it consists of different groups, each of them has its own characteristics" [1]. This class can be conditionally divided into several main groups. The group of large owners includes owners of large enterprises, banks, shopping centers and other large assets. They play an important role in the country's economy and often have the ability to influence the political decision-making process.

Economist B. Rozmetov comes to the following conclusion in his research: "Large owners are the locomotive of the economy of Uzbekistan, they serve as the main source of investments and innovations" [2]. The medium owner group includes owners of medium-sized businesses, including owners of medium-sized manufacturing enterprises, service industry facilities, and retail outlets. They play an important role in ensuring the stability of the country's economy and form the basis of the middle class.

Sociologist D. As Rahmonov noted, "The middle class of owners is a guarantee of socio-economic stability in Uzbekistan" [3]. The group of small owners consists of small businesses and individual entrepreneurs, as well as individuals who own their own housing and other small property. They are the largest and fastest growing part of the country's economy. Economist S. In his research, Gulyamov concludes as follows: "Small owners are the most dynamic and flexible part of the economy of Uzbekistan, they take a leading position in creating new jobs and introducing innovations" [4]. The group of owners in the agricultural sector includes farmers and farm owners. In the conditions of Uzbekistan, this group is of particular importance, because agriculture is an important branch of the country's economy.

Professor Sh. As Shodmonov noted, "Owners in the field of agriculture play an important role not only in ensuring food security, but also in maintaining socio-economic stability in rural areas" [5]. Intellectual property owners are a relatively new but increasingly important group that includes owners of copyrights, patents, trademarks, and other intellectual property. Economist N. According to Sirojiddinov, "Intellectual property owners play a crucial role in Uzbekistan's innovative development and transition to a knowledge-based economy" [6].

A number of factors influence the formation and development of the property class. One of the important factors is the state's economic policy and legal framework. Laws and decrees adopted in Uzbekistan on the protection of property rights, support of entrepreneurship and improvement of the investment environment

created a legal basis for the development of the owner class. Economist A. As Vahabov noted, "The state's policy of property rights protection creates important conditions for the stable development of the owner class" [7]. The general economic situation in the country and the level of development of market relations is also an important factor. If the owner class grows rapidly during periods of economic growth, its growth may slow down or even shrink during times of economic crisis.

In this regard, Professor M. Sharifhojaev expresses the following opinion: "The dynamics of the development of the ownership class in Uzbekistan is directly related to the general economic growth rates of the country" [8]. The educational system and the level of entrepreneurial culture of the population are also important factors. The qualitative development of the owner class largely depends on the population's education level, professional qualifications and entrepreneurial skills. In this regard, reforms in the field of education carried out in Uzbekistan, including the wide introduction of teaching the basics of entrepreneurship, are of great importance. The role of the propertied class in society is multifaceted and includes not only economic but also social and political aspects. The owner class is the main driving force of the country's economic development. They contribute to economic growth through investment, job creation and innovation. The propertied class plays an important role in ensuring social stability. They form the basis of the middle class and help reduce social inequality in society. The owning class has the ability to influence political processes, and they often form various public organizations and business associations to protect their interests. However, there are a number of problems in the development of the ownership class in Uzbekistan. These include issues such as corruption, bureaucratic obstacles, limited access to financial resources, and sometimes insufficient protection of property rights. Complex measures are being implemented by the state to solve these problems, including improving the legal framework, simplifying administrative procedures, and strengthening the mechanisms for protecting the rights of owners.

Summary

In short, the composition and structure of the ownership class in Uzbekistan is complex and dynamic, and it plays an important role in the country's socio-economic development. Further development and strengthening of the class of owners is an important condition for ensuring stable economic growth and social well-being of Uzbekistan. Support and encouragement of this process remains one of the priority areas of state policy.

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